

SCIANCE

D6.2

**Strategic Advisory
Board Engagement Plan**

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Abstract	
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<p>The Strategic Advisory Board (SAB) of the SCIANCE project provides high-level guidance to ensure the scientific and strategic quality of project outputs. Composed of leading experts from European and international organisations, the SAB advises on project outputs (research priorities, infrastructure upgrade scenarios, cooperation mechanisms, and sustainability pathways), facilitates alignment with broader European initiatives and stakeholder engagement.</p>	

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Terminology / Acronyms	
RAISE	Resource for AI Science in Europe
SAB	Strategic Advisory Board
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda

Table of Contents

1	SCIANCE Project	3
2	Strategic Advisory Board	3
2.1	Role of the Strategic Advisory Board	3
2.2	Duties and responsibilities	3
2.3	Strategic Advisory Board members	4
2.4	Strategic Advisory Board meetings	4

1 SCIANCE Project

The SCIANCE project is a European coordination initiative establishing the foundations for the Resource for AI Science in Europe (RAISE). The project promotes interdisciplinary collaboration to integrate AI into scientific research by enabling streamlined access to trustworthy data repositories, computing resources, and research infrastructures across Europe. Bringing together leading research infrastructures, scientific organisations, and AI centres of excellence, SCIANCE develops a Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) through an iterative co-creation process.

Building on a comprehensive AI-in-science landscape analysis, the SRIA identifies long-term research challenges where AI can accelerate discovery and defines cross-domain AI research and innovation priorities, focusing on open, trustworthy, and frugal AI methods for science. A roadmap for infrastructure upgrades and cooperation mechanisms supports its implementation, translating scientific research and innovation priorities into coordinated action. To consolidate the European AI-in-science ecosystem, SCIANCE pilots the RAISE Secretariat, supported by the RAISE Digital Hub, community-building events at annual AIS Summits, and the RAISE Academy, providing a continuous framework for engagement, capacity building, knowledge sharing, and cross-domain collaborations.

By combining scientific domain expertise with AI research and infrastructure knowledge, SCIANCE delivers robust, evidence-based guidance that is scientifically credible and strategically aligned with European Commission objectives, laying the foundations for future collaborative, AI-enabled science in Europe.

2 Strategic Advisory Board

The SCIANCE project will rely on a Strategic Advisory Board (SAB) consisting of high-level representatives from key European and international organisations and initiatives, to provide knowledgeable inputs to the conceptual and methodological developments of the project and the most efficient exploitation of project results and outputs.

2.1 Role of the Strategic Advisory Board

The SAB will provide strategic guidance, advise on project outputs (research priorities, infrastructure upgrade scenarios, cooperation mechanisms and sustainability pathways), facilitate connections with wider European initiatives, contribute to alignment with broader European and Member State priorities and facilitate their implementation and endorsement by key European AI in Science actors. In addition, the SCIANCE consortium will approach SAB Members with specific questions for feedback about aspects of the project that relate to their individual expertise.

The SAB acts solely in an advisory, non-binding role in the project. Its recommendations and feedback are considered facultative and may be incorporated after review and consideration by the SCIANCE Management Committee.

2.2 Duties and responsibilities

The SAB has an active advisory role in the project and ensures systematic dialogue with strategic European initiatives, infrastructures and networks throughout the project, from knowledge consolidation (Phase 1) to the identification of Research and Innovations priorities (Phase 2) and SRIA and roadmap development (Phase 3).

Inputs and recommendations from the Strategic Advisory Board on key project deliverables will be collected through a dedicated consultation process coordinated by the SCIANCE Coordinator.

The role of the SAB comprises the following aspects:

- Maintain a close advisory partnership with the SCIANCE project by participating in regular SAB meetings and provide expertise when approached by the consortium with specific questions.
- Provide insights and inputs to support the SCIANCE project outputs, in particular by providing feedback on:
 - The accuracy and relevance of the state of the art for scientific research using AI for each pilot scientific pilot area (D1.1) and for AI research and innovations relevant for scientific research (D1.2)
 - The robustness of the AI in science landscape analysis (D1.4) and registry of good practices in AI-enabled Science (D1.5)
 - The relevance of strategic priorities identified for long-term scientific research challenges (D2.1), AI for science research and innovation priorities (D2.2) and interdisciplinary AI cooperation priorities (D3.1)
 - The feasibility of infrastructure upgrade scenarios and AI in science cooperation framework (D4.1) and associated implementation roadmap (D4.2)
 - Aligning the AI in Science Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA, D5.1) with existing strategic roadmaps, initiatives
- Open up and facilitate professional networks to advance SCIANCE project activities and recognition, by identifying relevant stakeholders and engagement opportunities and liaising with key initiatives, networks and events.
- Support coordination activities for RAISE and building the European AI in science community, by relaying SCIANCE dissemination activities and assisting with the uptake of SCIANCE outputs.

2.3 Strategic Advisory Board members

At the time of the first submission of this deliverable, the members of the Strategic Advisory Board had not yet been formally identified. The composition outlined below indicate the intended profiles and strategic affiliations to ensure balanced representation across research, infrastructure, policy and industry domains relevant to AI in science.

The Strategic Advisory Board (SAB) will consist of 9 external experts. This deliverable will be updated and resubmitted once all SAB members have been formally appointed.

Strategic Advisory Board		
Name	Organisation / Entity	Description
	To be identified	large scientific infrastructure, link to EIROForum
	To be identified	link to Science for AI, GenAI4EU Hub, ADRA, ELLIS
	To be identified	link to AI infrastructures, AI factories
	To be identified	link to AI industry
	To be identified	link to EOSC, data spaces
	To be identified	link to scientific infrastructures, ESFRI roadmaps
	To be identified	link to international AI in science efforts, potential participation in RAISE (HE associated countries)
	ERA action on AI in Science	link to ERA action on AI in science (chair), member states and stakeholders
	GenAI4EU Central Hub	Coordination with RAISE Science for AI activities

To mitigate risks related to limited availability of high-level experts, each SAB member will nominate one senior colleague to serve as deputy.

2.4 Strategic Advisory Board meetings

The Strategic Advisory Board convene at least twice during the project (e.g. around mid-term review and prior to final reporting), participate in relevant AIS Summit sessions, and as observers in the project General Assembly meetings. The project partners are invited to attend the Strategic Advisory Board meetings. In case the SAB meetings cannot be arranged for practical reasons, the meetings can be replaced by individual, written contributions by the SAB Members. Discussions and feedback from the SAB meetings will be recorded in minutes of the meeting by the SCIANCE coordinator.